

Research Paper

High-temperature heat pumps for geothermal applications in Africa: thermodynamic, economic and environmental evaluation[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Geothermal resources in Africa, from low- to high-enthalpy, remain underutilized despite their vast potential. The Rift Valley is rich in high-enthalpy resources for electricity generation, while the mainland offers abundant medium- and low-enthalpy sources suitable for diverse applications. This study explores the use of high-temperature heat pumps (HTHPs) with geothermal energy. The research develops a predictive model to assess the thermodynamic performance, economic viability, and environmental impact of large-scale HTHP deployment. The metamodels estimate key parameters such as installed capacity, heat output, and the Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOH). Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) quantifies environmental impact using a parametric Life Cycle Inventory (pLCI), linking HTHP construction impacts with thermodynamic performance. A key innovation of this study is its holistic approach, integrating technical, economic, and environmental evaluations to provide a comprehensive sustainability assessment. Environmental aspects focused exclusively on the Climate Change (CC) indicator. Unlike previous research, focused mainly on thermodynamics, this study includes cost analysis and environmental impact assessments using LCA methodologies. It also emphasizes real-world applications in Africa, where geothermal resources remain largely untapped. To bridge this gap, the model is applied to a Malawi case study, assessing hot-spring resources for sustainable cooking and vegetable drying, with direct socio-economic benefits. Population density maps identify optimal user areas, showcasing HTHP feasibility in off-grid settings. Results highlight the potential of low-enthalpy geothermal energy for cost-effective, sustainable heating and industrial applications, reinforcing its role in Africa's energy transition. This study provides a replicable framework for advancing geothermal resource utilization and supporting sustainability goals within the LEAP-RE Project.

1. Introduction

The African continent is endowed with significant geothermal potential, particularly concentrated in the eastern and southern regions, aligned with the East African Rift System (EARS) [1]. This geological phenomenon presents a promising avenue for the utilization of geothermal energy resources, due to the correlation between geothermal activity and Quaternary volcanism along the rift axis [2,3]. Moreover, Kenya's Rift Valley stands out as a hotspot for geothermal exploration and exploitation, boasting vast reserves estimated at 10,000 MW spread across 14 sites [4–6]. While conventional geothermal power plants have historically focused on high enthalpy resources, recent advancements have shed light on the untapped potential of medium to low enthalpy resources [7,8]. Notably, the adoption of cascading approaches,

leveraging different temperature levels of geothermal energy, emerges as a promising strategy to maximize resource utilization efficiency [9–11]. The direct utilization of geothermal energy is the oldest and most versatile way to harness geothermal energy of medium and low enthalpy. Current trending direct uses are mainly for heating systems working directly or through heat pumps, aquaculture, drying crops, growing plants and vegetables in greenhouses, processes of the paper and the cement industry, food processing, brewing, dyeing of fabrics, snow melting, cooling spaces and balneology, among others [12,13].

In this context, Africa stands at the forefront of harnessing geothermal energy for sustainable development [6]. This underscores the continent's commitment to transitioning towards cleaner and more reliable energy sources to meet growing energy demands while mitigating environmental impacts [11].

However, the use and the expansion of geothermal energy is

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Nomenclature		System	
<i>General</i>		COP	Coefficient of performance
HTHP	High temperature heat pump	Q_{evap}	Thermal power evaporator
GAA	Geothermal atlas for Africa	Q_{cond}	Thermal power condenser
n_p	number of intervals	m_{cycle}	working fluid flow rate
HFO	Hydrofluoroolefins	W_{comp}	Compressor's work requirement
<i>Economic</i>		T_{geo}	Geothermal temperature
C_{PO}	Cost of machinery reference pressure	m_{geo}	Geothermal mass flow rate
F_p	Pressure factor	<i>Scenarios</i>	
C_{BM}	Cost bare module	Hm	High mass flow rate
C_{valve}	Cost of the valve	Mm	Medium mass flow rate
C_{well}	Cost of the well	Lm	Low mass flow rate
C_i	Cost of single machinery	CS	Cooking station
T_{EW}	Total cost of equipment and wells	CD	Cassava drying
C_{DPI}	Total direct permanent investment	LT	Low users temperature
C_{TDC}	Total depreciable capital	HT	High users temperature
C_{TPI}	Cost total permanent investment	<i>Subscript</i>	
C_{TCI}	Total capital investment	5 k	5 thousand people
LCOH	Levelized cost of heat	10 k	6 thousand people
<i>Environmental</i>		50 k	7 thousand people
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment	10	10 thousand tons of cassava
pLCI	Parametric life cycle inventory	25	25 thousand tons of cassava
GWP	Global warming potential	80	80 thousand tons of cassava
CC	Climate change indicator		

hampered by several major challenges. First, the sector demands heavy upfront investments—for exploration, drilling, and building power plants—that can deter investors due to the high initial financial burden [14]. In fact, the cost of drilling an exploratory well can run into millions of dollars, and the uncertainty of discovering commercially viable resources only adds to the risk [15,16].

Furthermore, the long development timeline—from preliminary surveys to operational plants—complicates funding efforts because of extended payback periods and financial uncertainty [17–19]. On top of this, unclear policies and an underdeveloped regulatory framework, compounded by poor coordination between national and local institutions, further impede progress [14].

Additionally, the lack of adequately trained professionals in the geothermal field limits efficient development and maintenance of the infrastructure. Environmental and social concerns also emerge, as the construction and operation of geothermal projects can disturb natural ecosystems and potentially lead to the displacement of local communities [20]. Finally, technological shortcomings—such as outdated equipment and insufficient transmission networks—and a weak political commitment to creating robust regulatory systems continue to obstruct the full exploitation of geothermal resources [20,21].

In this geothermal challenging context, acquiring detailed data on geothermal resource conditions and evaluating geothermal potential using advanced engineering applications is essential. A comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach that integrates energy, economic, and environmental assessments can provide stakeholders with a holistic understanding of the benefits associated with the sustainable utilization of geothermal resources. Such an approach not only supports more informed decision-making but also encourages strategic investments and policy developments that contribute to a resilient and competitive energy sector.

For this reason, in this paper the application of High Temperature Heat Pump (HTHP) for steam production is investigated. Integration of HTHP with geothermal systems offers potential energy consumption benefits [22].

A review of the existing literature reveals that the application of HTHP technologies in the geothermal sector has been explored by only a limited number of authors [22–25]. Despite the growing interest in innovative solutions for geothermal energy, research on HTHP remains fragmented and incomplete.

Jeßberger et al. [23] investigate the potential enhancement of existing geothermal plants through the integration of large-scale heat pumps. The study assesses the LCOH and conducts sensitivity analyses on geological, design, and economic parameters. Focusing on a district heating case study south of Munich, the system delivers heat at an average temperature of 85 °C. Geothermal system costs are excluded, aligning with the approach of upgrading existing plants. Ungar et al. [22] provide a robust thermodynamic basis for evaluating various geothermal HTHP configurations for industrial steam production, highlighting the potential of water-based systems and the limitations of CO₂ systems. However, economic assessments and experimental validation are needed to fully evaluate the practical feasibility of these technologies. Lu et al. [25] presents a thermodynamic analysis of a HTHP system for steam generation using medium–low temperature geothermal water. The study lacks a detailed economic assessment, limiting evaluation of its cost-effectiveness compared to alternative technologies. System optimization focuses on thermodynamic parameters, overlooking factors such as component sizing, costs, and environmental impact. Results are based on specific operating conditions, potentially limiting their generalizability. Kim et al. [24] present a HTHP system design using moderate-temperature geothermal water. The study focuses on a hybrid compression/absorption heat pump capable of producing temperatures above 90 °C and as low as 20 °C using 50 °C geothermal water. The innovative hybrid system combines compression and absorption cycles but introduces greater complexity, potentially increasing maintenance costs and reducing reliability. Like Lu et al. [25], it lacks a detailed economic analysis, limiting assessment of its cost-effectiveness. While the system could reduce global CO₂ emissions by up to 8 %, the study does not provide a comprehensive comparison of greenhouse gas emissions with alternative technologies.

In summary, several aspects are noted in the literature:

- Many studies focus on thermodynamic performance but omit detailed economic assessments. This includes full cost evaluations—capital, operational, and maintenance costs—which are essential for comparing HTHP with alternative technologies.
- Although some studies mention potential CO₂ reductions, comprehensive, comparative analyses of greenhouse gas emissions across different HTHP configurations and alternative systems are lacking. Notably, no studies have investigated the environmental impacts of HTHP technologies using established methodologies such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA).
- The generalizability of results is limited by analyses performed under specific operating conditions. Additionally, issues related to the integration of HTHP systems with existing geothermal infrastructures and district heating networks are not fully explored.

These gaps are particularly significant, given the increasing importance of sustainability as a key criterion for developing new energy technologies.

Furthermore, literature lacks applied studies analyzing real implementations of HTHP systems, leaving an important research area regarding the technical and operational challenges of this technology unaddressed. These lacks are especially remarkable within the African Continent, where the energy transition is at its infancy and the nexus between several novel energy technologies and territorial resources is undisclosed yet at a large extent. Incorporating an LCA-based approach would allow for a comprehensive evaluation of environmental impacts, fostering the development of more sustainable solutions and supporting the broader adoption of HTHP technology in the geothermal sector.

The aim of this paper is to address the gap identified in the scientific literature by proposing a simplified large-scale model for assessing the sustainability of HTHP technologies combined with geothermal energy.

The model is structured to evaluate a wide range of thermal capacities and to supply heat to users at different temperature levels. Additionally, it produces specific results related to economic and environmental parameters, providing a holistic and comprehensive sustainability analysis. The environmental model is based on the LCA approach. In addition, to also meet the gap in the African context the model is applied to an African case study, Malawi hot-springs, exploring

multiple scenarios involving applications such as sustainable cooking and vegetable drying—applications that could improve the quality of life for local populations. For this reason, population density maps are used to assess the potential user area that could benefit from these solutions.

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2. Methodologies

The methodology of this study presents a comparative analysis of two High-Temperature Heat Pump (HTHP) system configurations, as shown in Fig. 1.

- Cycle A features a single pressure level and includes an evaporator, compressor, condenser, and expansion valve.
- Cycle B operates with two pressure levels and incorporates a separator at an intermediate pressure, positioned between the system's minimum and maximum pressures.

The separator plays a key role in recovering heat from the working fluid after condensation and reducing the compressor's workload, ultimately enhancing the system's coefficient of performance (COP).

Both system configurations are based on the work of Cao et al. [26] and use R152 as the working fluid. To validate the thermodynamic model, the input conditions specified in the study by Cao et al. [26] were replicated. The model was validated by comparing the thermal capacities of the mechanical components, resulting in a deviation of approximately 0.5 % from Cao's findings. The same refrigerant, R152, was used throughout the validation process.

Although hydrocarbons such as R600a and R290 are commonly used in regions where low-cost solutions are preferred, the choice made in this study is primarily driven by environmental considerations. Specifically, low-Global Warming Potential (GWP) HFOs, e.g. R1233zd(E) and R1234ze(Z) refrigerants were selected as more sustainable alternatives. Moreover, these refrigerants enable higher condenser temperatures compared to R152a, R600a, or R290, allowing for increased supply temperatures while still operating within subcritical cycle conditions, as required in the model of this work.

Fig. 1. Plant layout of the two cycles: A on the left, B on the right.

These models are designed to evaluate the performance of the two cycles by analyzing several key variables. These include the thermal power of the evaporator (Q_{evap}), which represents the heat absorbed from the geothermal fluid, and the heat output from the condenser (Q_{cond}), indicating the system's useful thermal power. Additionally, the work required by the compressor (W_{comp}), is considered, along with the coefficient of performance (COP) of the system. The models also assess the flow rate of the working fluid (m_{cycle}), the flow rate of the generated hot water ($m_{\text{w,out}}$), and the temperature of the hot water output ($T_{\text{w,out}}$). Once the key parameters of the thermodynamic model have been identified, it is connected to the economic and environmental models. These models evaluate economic and environmental parameters, enabling a comprehensive assessment of the HTHP system. A detailed description of each model is provided in [Sections 2.1 Thermodynamic Modeling](#), [2.2 Thermo-Economic Modeling](#), and [2.3 Environmental Modeling](#).

The innovative approach, which allows the developed models to be extended to a wide range of applications in terms of size, energy performance, and economic and environmental outcomes, involves the generation of metamodels for each key parameter. A metamodel is a simplified version of a more complex system, which reduces computational costs [27]. The process began by defining the basic inputs for the thermodynamic model: geothermal temperature (T_{geo}), geothermal mass flow rate (m_{geo}), and the extraction well depth. A variation range was established for each parameter: 50–100 °C for T_{geo} , 1–50 kg/s for m_{geo} , and 0–15000 m for the well depth. Next, a set number of calculation intervals (n_p) was defined for each range, resulting in three input matrices with dimensions of $n_p \times n_p$. Then, all possible input combinations were evaluated using the thermodynamic, economic, and environmental models, with the thermodynamic model being optimized each time to achieve the maximum thermal capacity at the evaporator. The results from the various models were compiled into output matrices, covering mechanical component sizes (kW), basic cycle parameters (pressure, temperature, flow rate, etc.), component costs (\$), thermo-economic costs (\$/kWh), and environmental indicators (kg CO₂ eq/kWh). Finally, by performing multidimensional interpolation on each output matrix, the metamodels were generated for the following parameters: Q_{evap} , Q_{cond} , W_{comp} , m_{cycle} , COP, LCOH, and CC. The number n_p was determined through an iterative process, meaning it is set when the metamodel achieves a relative mean prediction error of 0.5 % compared to the initial model.

Based on the structure of the model, it allows for the evaluation of scenarios that either use surface geothermal water or involve extraction from shallow wells. It is important to note that the thermodynamic metamodel's efficacy is independent on well depth. However, the metamodel's thermo-economic and environmental impact are significantly influenced by the presence and depth of geothermal wells, as highlighted in recent studies [28,29]. Accordingly, this study engages on a comprehensive thermo-economic and environmental analysis across three scenarios: surface geothermal water extraction (well₀₀), extraction from a 500 m well coupled with reinjection into a 300 m well (well₅₀₀), and extraction from a 1000 m well with reinjection into a 600 m well (well₁₀₀₀).

2.1. Thermodynamic modeling

In the first configuration, marked as Cycle A operating at a single pressure level, the geothermal fluid is introduced into the evaporator. Here, it transfers heat to the working fluid, which flows in counter-current.

On the geothermal side, the outlet temperature ($T_{\text{geo,out}}$) is fixed at 45 °C, while the inlet temperature ($T_{\text{geo,in}}$), as specified in [Section 2](#), varies between 50 °C and 100 °C. Therefore, the temperature difference (ΔT_{geo}) is variable, ranging from a minimum of 5 °C to a maximum of 55 °C. On the HTHP side, the temperatures T_{a1} and T_{a2} , as well as T_{b4} and T_{b5} , are set, with the temperature differences at the evaporator inlet

($\Delta T_{\text{evap,in}}$) and outlet ($\Delta T_{\text{evap,out}}$) being dependent on the geothermal conditions, as described in Eqs. (1)–(3).

$$\Delta T_{\text{geo}} = T_{\text{geo,in}} - T_{\text{geo,out}} \quad (1)$$

$$T_{a1}, T_{b4} = T_{\text{geo,out}} - \Delta T_{\text{evap,out}} \quad (2)$$

$$T_{a2}, T_{b5} = T_{\text{geo,in}} - \Delta T_{\text{evap,in}} \quad (3)$$

After this step, the evaporator and mass flow rate in the cycle (m_{cycle}) can be evaluated using Eqs. (4) and (5), where $h_{\text{geo,in}}$ and $h_{\text{geo,out}}$ represents the enthalpy of the fluid at the inlet and outlet conditions, respectively

$$Q_{\text{evap}} = m_{\text{geo}} \cdot (h_{\text{geo,in}} - h_{\text{geo,out}}) \quad (4)$$

$$m_{\text{cycle}} = Q_{\text{evap}} / (h_{a2} - h_{a1}) \quad (5)$$

The working fluid, which exists either as saturated vapor ($x = 1$) or superheated steam, enters the compressor. The compressor is responsible for increasing the fluid pressure to match that of the condenser and it is calculated as Eq. (6). The power required by the compressor is evaluated by considering the pressure conditions at the inlet and outlet streams of the compressor, while also accounting for the device's efficiency, set at etacomp.

$$W_{\text{comp}} = m_{\text{cycle}} \cdot (h_{a3} - h_{a2}) \quad (6)$$

The operating conditions of the condenser have been set. Specifically, the pressure corresponds to the saturation pressure of the fluid at the condensation temperature (T_{cond}). This temperature is selected based on the intended application. In the model, two different temperature levels are considered:

- low-temperature (LT) level set at 105 °C
- high-temperature (HT) level set at 140 °C

On the user side, the water is assumed to be drawn at an inlet temperature of 50 °C ($T_{\text{us,in}}$) from various sources such as residential, commercial, or industrial applications. The water is then heated to an outlet temperature ($T_{\text{us,out}}$) which is determined using Eq. (7). Thus, the condenser is evaluated using Eq. (8):

$$T_{\text{us,out}} = T_{\text{cond}} - \Delta T_{\text{cond}} \quad (7)$$

$$Q_{\text{cond}} = m_{\text{cycle}} \cdot (h_{a3} - h_{a0}) \quad (8)$$

By utilizing the heat output provided by the condenser, the flow rate of hot water that can be produced at this temperature is determined. Finally, the expansion valve reduces the working fluid pressure back to the evaporator conditions, thereby completing the thermodynamic cycle.

Finally, the COP is evaluated using Eq. (9).

$$\text{COP} = (Q_{\text{cond}} / W_{\text{comp}}) \quad (9)$$

In configuration (B), a separator is integrated into the cycle. Following the initial expansion undergone by the fluid in the high-pressure expansion valve, the separator segregates saturated liquid from saturated vapor. The former undergoes further expansion in a second expansion valve until it reaches the evaporator pressure. Meanwhile, the latter is blended with the fluid exiting the low-pressure compressor. This mixture is subsequently pressurized to match the condenser pressure by the high-pressure compressor.

The intermediate pressure at the separator has also been optimized to achieve the maximum COP in configuration B. The optimized values are reported in [Table 1](#) for each fluid and for both LT and HT scenarios. [Table 1](#) reports the main parameters for both cycles. One important aspect to highlight is the influence of different refrigerants in the model. The selected fluids, R1234ze(z) and R1233zd(e), have relatively similar characteristics in terms of critical pressure ($P_{c,R1234ze(z)} = 39.7$ bar; P_c ,

Table 1
Main thermodynamic parameter for the cycles.

Parameters		Value	Unit
Geothermal fluid outlet temperature	$T_{geo,out}$	45	°C
Evaporator inlet temperature difference	$\Delta T_{evap,in}$	5	°C
Evaporator outlet temperature difference	$\Delta T_{evap,out}$	9	°C
Compressor isentropic efficiency	η_{comp}	0.8	
Inlet temperature of the supplied water	$T_{us,in}$	50	°C
Temperature difference between critical point and condenser	ΔT_{cond}	10	°C
Condenser outlet temperature difference	$\Delta T_{cond,out}$	5	°C
Separator pressure LT for R1234ze(z)	P_{LT}	7.6	bar
Separator pressure HT for R1234ze(z)	P_{HT}	13.4	bar
Separator pressure LT for R1233zd (e)	P_{LT}	5.8	bar
Separator pressure HT for R1233zd(e)	P_{HT}	10.4	bar

R1234zd(e) = 35.7 bar) and critical temperature ($T_{c,R1234ze(z)} = 153$ °C; $T_{c,R1234zd(e)} = 165.5$ °C). As a result, their performance differs from other refrigerants, such as R152, under these conditions, particularly in terms of system efficiency and the temperature level at which heat is delivered to the user. This aspect is further examined in Section 4.1.

The final output of the metamodel is a surface which depends on the two inputs (T_{geo} , m_{geo}) and represents a thermodynamic parameter of the cycle. For better understanding, the metamodel derived from linear multidimensional interpolation is shown in Fig. 2, with Cycle A featuring fluid R1233zd(E) as an example.

2.2. Thermo-economic modeling

The economic evaluation has two main stages. First, the cost of each individual plant component is estimated using the thermo-economic correlations proposed by Turton [30]. Then, the initial investment cost, along with total operating and maintenance costs, is assessed to calculate the Levelized Cost of Heating (LCOH).

The thermodynamic analysis provides key parameters needed for the thermo-economic correlations. These include the heat transfer surface area required for the condenser and evaporator, the flow rates handled

by the compressor and valve, and the volume flow rate in the separator. For heat exchangers, the parameter S, which represents the size of the mechanical component, corresponds to the surface area. This is determined using the thermal potential obtained from the thermodynamic model (expressed in kW), the logarithmic mean temperature difference (evaluated using Eq. (10)), and the global heat transfer coefficient U, which is set to 1.8 kW/(m² K) for the condenser and 2.5 kW/(m² K) for the evaporator. In Eq. (11), Q_{HE} represents the nominal heat power of either the condenser or the evaporator.

Table 2
Main equations for the thermo-economic model.

Cost	Correlation	
Evaporator, condenser, compressor	$CP_0 = 10^{K_1+K_2 \log_{10} S + K_3 \log_{10} S^2} F_p = 10^{C_1+C_2 \log_{10} P+C_3 \log_{10} P^2} C_{BM} = CP_0 * (B_1 + B_2 * F_M * F_p)$	All variables are indicated in the tables of Turton 2008
Valve	$C_{valve} = 114.5 * m_{cycle}$	[47]
Wells	$C_{well} = 2500 * m_{drilled}$	[28]
Total cost of equipment and wells	$T_{EW} = \sum_i^{nc} C_i + C_{well}$	C_i cost of single component
Total direct permanent investment	$C_{DPI} = T_{EW} + C_{site} + C_{serv}$	C_{well} cost of the wells C_{site} cost of site preparation C_{serv} cost of service facilities
Total depreciable capital	$C_{TDC} = C_{DPI} + C_{cont}$	C_{cont} cost of contingencies
Cost total permanent investment	$C_{TPI} = C_{TDC} + C_{land} + C_{royal} + C_{startup}$	C_{royal} cost of royalties C_{land} cost of land $C_{startup}$ cost of plant startup
Total capital investment	$C_{TCI} = C_{TPI} + C_{WC}$	C_{WC} cost of working capital

CP_0 = Purchase component to ambient pressure; S = capacity or size parameter for the equipment; K_n = Turton table value; F_p = pressure factor, F_M = Material factor; BM = Bare module; C_i =Cost of single machinery; B_n = Turton Costant.

Fig. 2. Cycle_a fluid R1233zd(E).

For the separator, present in the Cycle B only, the thermo-economic correlation referenced from Mosaffa et al. [31] is adopted. Table 2 outlines the component types and equations used for each one. Various economic equations exist for geothermal wells, often following linear correlations. In this study, the correlation proposed by Shamoushaki et al. [28] is adopted. LCOH is a techno-economic parameter fundamental for feasibility assessment, enabling the economic comparison of thermal systems. As reported in Eq. (12), it quantifies the cost of heat produced per kilowatt-hour (\$/kWh), as discussed by de Simón-Martín et al. [32].

$$\Delta T_{ml} = \frac{\Delta T_{hot} - \Delta T_{cold}}{\log((\Delta T_{hot}/\Delta T_{cold}))} \quad (10)$$

$$S_{HE} = (Q_{HE}/(U \cdot \Delta T_{ml})) \quad (11)$$

$$LCOH = \frac{C_{TCI} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{C_{O\&M}}{(1+r)^i}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{E_i}{(1+r)^i}} \quad (12)$$

C_{TCI} is the total capital investment cost, $C_{O\&M}$ is the annual operating and maintenance cost, E_i is the annual produced heat, r is the discount rate and n is the lifetime of the energy system. For the calculation of C_{TCI} , the method and parameters used in this work were taken from Karimi and Mansouri, [33] and Shamoushaki et al. [34] and readapted to the case of HTHP, as shown in Table 2. On the other hand, the yearly O&M cost was taken from Beckers et al. [35] for the general part. The cost of electricity, set at \$0.15/kWh and the total energy consumed by the compressors are taken from the above discussed thermodynamic metamodels. Furthermore, a 7 % discount rate and a useful life of 25 years were assumed.

2.3. Environmental modeling

The environmental modeling approach is based on the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology, outlined by ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards [36,37]. The approach used is cradle-to-gate, so the system boundaries include the production and reinjection geothermal wells (if present), the piping system, the surface plant, and the utilization phase. The functional unit for the analysis is the thermal kWh produced by the HTHP system. Specifically, to facilitate the assessment across numerous scenarios, emphasis was placed on developing a Parametric Life Cycle Inventory (pLCI). pLCI links material and energy consumption throughout the production, O&M of the HTHP system with its size, as determined by the thermodynamic metamodel. For the construction phase of the system, primary data were collected from commercially available HTHP models sourced from TRANE [38]. A correlation was established between system thermal power (kW) and total weight, as

Fig. 3. Development of correlation between total system weight and nominal HTHP heating capacity.

reported in Fig. 3, based on the collected data. Subsequently, the production process – *heat pump production, brine-water, 10 kW (heat pump, brine-water, 10 kW)* – from the Ecoinvent database was selected as a reference model [39]. Inputs and outputs of this process were categorized into materials and energy utilized during construction. Percentages for each material and energy consumption were determined, with energy normalized to the total mass of the element, as reported in Table 3. This allowed the creation of a new environmental model for the HTHP, incorporating adjusted input and output values multiplied by the correlation obtained in Fig. 3. The modeling of geothermal wells was approached linearly, utilizing a shallow well drilling process as described by [40]. The operation phase accounted for electricity consumption using a reference process for electricity production (*market for electricity, medium voltage | electricity, medium voltage, KE*) while maintenance was evaluated as a 20 % material replenishment throughout the whole life cycle. For the analysis, the Ecoinvent 3.7.1 database [39] and the Brightway software, integrated with activity-browser software via Python, were employed. The environmental impact, primarily focused on the Climate Change (CC) indicator, is expressed through the Environmental Footprint 3.1 methodology.

3. Case studies: Malawi hot springs

The case study evaluated in this paper is the Malawi hot springs. Davalos et al. [41] performed an extensive study on the geochemical characteristics of 27 hot springs in Malawi, distributed along north to south of the Malawi Rift Zone (MRZ). The Malawi Rift Zone (MRZ) is a magma-poor rift where geothermal potential is indicated by high heat flow and the presence of hot springs. Davalos et al. [41] examined 27 hot springs to estimate reservoir temperatures, investigate geochemical processes influencing water composition during ascent, and identify the most promising sites for geothermal energy development. During the dry season in July 2013, water samples were collected directly from the spring sources using the grab technique. These samples were filtered and stored in designated containers for anion, cation, and isotope analysis. In addition to the characteristics related to the chemistry of the geothermal resource, the surface temperature assessment is carried out by reporting the temperature of all 27 sites. It ranges between 35–80 °C, but only hot springs with a temperature above 50 °C are taken into consideration in this work, as reported in Table 4.

Unfortunately, the required mass flow rate are not available, for this reason, three flow rate scenarios are defined – High 50 kg/s (Hm), Medium 20 kg/s (Mm), Low 8 kg/s (Lm).

Final applications have been defined for possible users of the heat produced at the respective temperatures. In particular, two possible uses have been selected:

- Cooking station (CS) supplying steam at 140 °C (HT condition) for cooking food, which requires about 2.89 GWh/year heat load for a

Table 3

Material and energy flows relative to total weight evaluated by the correlation in Fig. 3.

Material / energy flows	Amount	Unit
copper	16.96	%
lubricating oil	1.31	%
polyvinylchloride	0.77	%
reinforcing steel	57.83	%
steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled	15.42	%
tube insulation, elastomere	7.71	%
Total weight (Tw)	Tw	Tons
Refrigerant R134a	0.02	kg/Tw
Electricity, medium Voltage	1.079414	kWh/Tw
heat, district or industrial, natural gas	10.25443	MJ/Tw
Water, unspecified natural origin	0.005459	m3/Tw

Table 4
Hot spring geothermal sites in Malawai [41].

Hot spring	Surface	Hot spring	Surface
	T °C		T °C
Ngala	54.9	Chombo	66.8
Chiweta	79.7	Madzimawira	63.7
Mphizi Stream	78.7	Ling'ona	58.1
Mtondolo	64.8	Chikwizi	52.2
Mtondolo 2	72.9	July Borehole	51.4
Chiwe	74.9		

group of 5,000 people, (CS_{5k}); 5.79 GWh/year for 10,000 people (CS_{10k}); 29.00 MWh/year for 50,000 people (CS_{50k}) [42].

- Cassava drying (CD) supplies steam at 100 °C (LT condition) for drying vegetables. This process requires about 306 kWh/(ton), so three scenarios are assumed in which a company produces about 10 k tons/year CD₁₀, 25 k tons/year CD₂₅, and 80 k tons/year CD₈₀ [43].

4. Results

4.1. Parametric analysis

This section presents the results obtained from the parametric analysis of the thermodynamic model introduced in Section 2.1. From the analysis conducted on the performance of the system depicted in Fig. 4, the COP in all scenarios within Cycle A and Cycle B are compared, referred to the above mentioned HFO and R152 fluids. COP is not m_{geo} dependent but only on T_{geo} , as the m_{cycle} increases and decreases at the same rate as m_{geo} , thus the COP does not change at variable m_{geo} . This analysis reveals how the results are affected by different refrigerants. As shown in the figure, high-temperature conditions for R152 are not reported. This is because the critical temperature of R152 is below 140 °C ($T_{c,R152} = 113$ °C), which prevents maintaining a subcritical cycle, making this refrigerant unsuitable for the working code. The general

trend is increasing because, as T_{geo} increases, the difference between high- and low-pressure decreases, so the compressor work is reduced and the COP increases. Focusing on the case of LT, the COP for HFO fluids ranges between 3.67 and 4.14 for Cycle A and between 3.53 and 4.13 for Cycle B. Despite the difference of pressure levels in this case, there is no remarkable difference between the two cycles at the thermodynamic level. Conversely, there is a notable performance difference with fluid R152, exhibiting consistently lower COP across all T_{geo} values. Considering that HFO's environmental performance is better than R152 due to its lower GWP and the better thermodynamic performance of the cycle, the selection of HFO fluids is advised. In addition, in the case of HT with HFOs, it is possible to maintain the subcritical cycle by increasing the output temperature. The comparative analysis between Cycle A and Cycle B unveils a notable downturn in COP for both cycles when juxtaposed with the LT scenario. Comparing LT and HT, COP of cycle A shows a sharp drop from 1.90 to 2.47. In Cycle B, albeit exhibiting a decrease compared to the preceding scenario, the COP ranges between 2.59 and 2.89. The rise of T_{cond} leads to a growth of pressure, consequently increasing the workload for the compressor. In spite of the higher temperature steam produced for the end user, at the same time the COP of the cycle is reduced. This behavior is enhanced in Cycle A, exerting a lower impact on Cycle B due to the presence of two compression levels, which mitigates the overall work required during the compression stage. For the following analyses, Cycle A for the LT scenario and Cycle B for the HT scenario are taken as references.

4.2. General results of metamodels: economic and environmental

This section presents the results obtained by applying the economic and environmental models introduced in Sections 2.2 and 2.3 for the generation of metamodels, as described in Section 2. Specifically, the results of the metamodels for the economic parameter LCOH and the environmental parameter CC are presented.

The thermo-economic evaluation reveals a significant variability in

Fig. 4. Comparison of COP for the different analyzed cycles.

LCOH, depending on the resource conditions and well characteristics. Fig. 5a–c shows the LCOH of well₁₀₀₀, well₅₀₀, and well₀₀ respectively. Additionally, the red dashed line represents the reference LCOH value provided by IEA [44] for heat generated from natural gas-fired boilers, hovering around 17c\$/kWh, while the cost obtained for HTHP is indicated as 22c\$/kWh [45]. It is clear the relevant decrease in LCOH from 5a to 5c, highlighting the significant influence of drilling costs on this parameter. In Fig. 5a, it is observed that LCOH is exceedingly high for low value of T_{geo} and m_{geo} , reaching a maximum of 163.4c\$/kWh, with economic feasibility only apparent at higher temperatures or increased mass flow rates, where LCOH drops to about 12.8c\$/kWh. In Fig. 5b, where the well depth is shallower, the maximum LCOH reduces to 100c\$/kWh, and more combinations of T_{geo} and m_{geo} below the red dashed line LCOH values. Finally, in Fig. 5c, only a narrow range fails to yield an economic advantage compared to literature data. In fact, for all combinations of T_{geo} and m_{geo} above 62°C or above 20 kg/s, an LCOH below the boiler heat output is obtained. This remarks the strongly affected dependence of LCOH on the cost of wells. Therefore, for HTHP applications, cases where the geothermal reservoir is superficial, hot waste fluids from geothermal power plants or other situations without drilling wells would offer significant economic benefits. However, if a greater number of wells or deeper drilling is necessary, the conditions for LCOH advantage are reduced considerably. Therefore, a careful evaluation is needed for each specific case, according to the depth of the available resource. The same contours for the LT case are not displayed due to the similar trend, with minimal change in LCOH range, (± 3 –6c\$/kWh).

Fig. 6 illustrates the metamodel of the environmental impact indicator (CC) for the same cases presented in Fig. 5. As noted in section 1, the literature on geothermal HTHP systems is extremely limited, with few studies available on their environmental impacts. Consequently, the reference values used for comparison are adopted from standard heat production systems provided by the Ecoinvent database and derived from LCA. Specifically, one reference value corresponds to a natural gas modulating condensing boiler producing 1 kWh at 264.16 g CO₂ eq/kWh (red line), while the other represents a borehole heat exchanger with a brine-water system, evaluated at 223.88 g CO₂ eq/kWh (blue line) [39].

The behavior is similar to the LCOH, where CC has a higher impact for case 6a, whereas for low m_{geo} and T_{geo} , 329 gCO₂ eq/kWh is found which very similar to normal boiler emissions. For this reason, temperatures above 67 °C or m_{geo} above 25 kg/s are preferred to have a low environmental impact, compared to other low-impact systems. Also, all the combination of m_{geo} and T_{geo} above the dashed blue line are favorable, as they correspond to a lower environmental impact. It should be considered that, also in this case, the impact of drilling has a major contribution, even though it is higher compared to the effect on LCOH, because CC is also strongly affected by electricity production. As shown in both Fig. 6b and 6c, the potential for achieving low environmental impact is even larger, confirmed by a decrease in equivalent emissions. The borehole heat exchanger brine-water limits given in Fig. 6b only cover a small range for temperatures below 53° C. On the other hand, from Fig. 6c all cases are environmentally advantageous.

Combining the information obtained from the economic (LCOH) and environmental (CC) metamodels, a cost-benefit or impact-benefit approach can be defined. Using reference values from the literature—17c\$/kWh for a gas boiler and 223.88 g CO₂ eq/kWh for a borehole heat exchanger with a brine-water system—as normalization thresholds for LCOH and CC, respectively, the metamodels can be normalized to derive a cost-benefit or impact-benefit ratio. If this ratio is less than 1, the resource conditions provide an economic or environmental benefit; if it is greater than 1, no benefit is obtained. Naturally, the lower the ratio, the more advantageous the system becomes.

As shown in Fig. 7, shallower geothermal resources allow for a broader range of T_{geo} and m_{geo} combinations that yield a cost-benefit or impact-benefit ratio below 1, orange dot-line. This implies that, under such conditions, the system delivers economic and environmental advantages relative to the reference thresholds.

Furthermore, among the constraints examined, economic feasibility stands out as the most critical factor, overshadowing environmental considerations. In practical terms, this means that parameters such as initial capital expenditure, operational costs, and maintenance expenses have a greater influence on system viability than environmental impacts like CO₂ emissions.

Consequently, when evaluating HTHP installations, it is advisable to

Fig. 5. Techno-economic metamodel of the LCOH parameter for the three well depth scenarios: 5a well₁₀₀₀, 5b well₅₀₀, 5c well₀₀.

Fig. 6. Environmental metamodel of the CC parameter for the three well depth scenarios: 5a well₁₀₀₀, 5b well₅₀₀, 5c well₀₀.

prioritize economic viability in the decision-making process. The optimal conditions derived from the economic metamodels—indicating the best balance of cost-efficiency and performance—should serve as the primary benchmark for project design and implementation.

4.3. Results of Malawi case studies

This section presents an in-depth analysis of the Malawi case study, where the complete metamodel—encompassing energy, economic, and environmental dimensions—is applied to evaluate the performance of geothermal heat utilization. As introduced in Section 3, this study focuses on Malawi's hot springs as a potential renewable energy source. The results for Cycle B, using R1234ze(Z) as the working fluid, are illustrated in Fig. 8, which provides a comprehensive overview of both thermal energy production and the associated cost and environmental impact metrics.

On the left side of Fig. 8, the graph displays the thermal energy produced by the system, with dashed red lines indicating the specific heat demand levels required for three different cooking station (CS) scenarios: CS_{5k}, CS_{10k}, and CS_{50k}. These values represent progressively larger community cooking demands, with CS_{5k} corresponding to small-scale operations, CS_{10k} representing medium-scale cooking stations, and CS_{50k} indicating large-scale community cooking facilities. The analysis of thermal performance under different operational conditions provides key insights into the feasibility of utilizing hot spring resources for cooking applications. Under Low (Lm) conditions, nearly all hot springs successfully achieve and sustain the CS_{5k} level, with the exception of July Borehole, Chikwizi, and Ngala. These three hot springs exhibit lower thermal energy output, making them unsuitable for small-scale cooking applications under minimal flow rate conditions.

Some of the most productive hot springs, such as Chiwe, Motondolo 2, and Mphizi Stream, demonstrate the ability to meet the thermal demand of CS_{10k}, even under Lm conditions. This finding is particularly

significant, as it suggests that these hot springs have sufficient energy output to support medium-sized cooking stations even when operating at lower flow rates. Under Medium (Mm) conditions, the thermal output of all hot springs increases, allowing all wells—except for July Borehole—to fully satisfy the CS_{10k} thermal load. In the case of July Borehole, the thermal energy falls just short of the requirement by approximately 1.6 %, indicating that a minor optimization or slight increase in operational flow rate could enable this hot spring to meet the CS_{10k} demand.

Finally, at the highest heat demand level (CS_{50k}), only a selected group of high-performing hot springs—Chombo, Chiwe, Motondolo, Motondolo 2, Mphizi Stream, and Chiweta—can reach or exceeding this threshold. The ability of these wells to supply sufficient energy for large-scale cooking stations is a crucial finding, highlighting their potential for supporting large communities. A particularly noteworthy observation is that some hot springs—such as Chiwe, Motondolo 2, and Mphizi Stream—produce thermal energy well above the CS_{50k} requirement. In certain cases, their output exceeds the assigned threshold by more than 50 %, emphasizing their potential as reliable, high-capacity geothermal energy sources. These findings reinforce the viability of geothermal heat for large-scale cooking applications, particularly in regions where access to affordable and sustainable energy sources is essential.

Beyond thermal performance, the economic feasibility of using geothermal energy for cooking applications is assessed by analyzing the LCOH. The right side of Fig. 8 presents the LCOH values for all evaluated hot springs. The LCOH across all hot springs remains within a highly competitive range of 11.2c\$/kWh to 12.5c\$/kWh, positioning geothermal heat as an economically viable alternative to conventional heating sources.

The primary reason for these notably low costs is the shallow depth of the geothermal resources being utilized. Since the hot springs are relatively close to the surface, the cost associated with well drilling is significantly reduced, minimizing its impact on the overall cost per kWh

Fig. 7. Cost-benefit and environmental impact-benefit of normalized metamodells at different well depths.

Fig. 8. Heat produced by cycle B with R1234ze(Z) fluid and corresponding LCOH and CC, for cooking station.

produced by the HTHP system. Despite some degree of cost variability, particularly for hot springs such as Ngala, Chikwizi, and July Borehole, the LCOH never exceeds 13.8c\$/kWh, even under the worst-case

scenarios—where resource temperatures are at their lowest and flow rates are minimal (Lm conditions). The variation bars on the graph highlight the economic fluctuations observed across different

operational conditions. However, these fluctuations remain relatively contained, reinforcing the economic stability and predictability of geothermal heat production for cooking applications. Overall, the results confirm that geothermal energy presents a cost-effective solution for community cooking stations, providing a low-cost, sustainable alternative to conventional fuel sources.

In addition to cost considerations, the environmental impact of geothermal heat utilization is assessed through the CC indicator, measured in gCO_2/kWh . The CC values range between $186 \text{ gCO}_2/\text{kWh}$ and $196 \text{ gCO}_2/\text{kWh}$, indicating moderate environmental impact. While these values are higher than those observed for the cassava drying application (Fig. 9), they remain significantly lower than conventional fossil-fuel-based heating systems. The green markers in Fig. 8 illustrate how the environmental impact varies more significantly compared to LCOH. This larger fluctuation in CC values suggests that environmental performance is more sensitive to variations in operational conditions than economic performance.

A consistent trend emerges, hot springs with higher environmental impacts correspond to those with lower resource temperatures. This pattern is explained by the thermodynamic behavior of the HTHP cycle. Lower geothermal temperatures create a greater pressure difference between the low- and high-temperature sides of the cycle, leading to higher compressor electricity consumption. This increased electricity demand translates into higher indirect CO_2 emissions, thereby elevating the CC values for lower-temperature hot springs.

Despite these variations, the overall CC values remain well below those of conventional energy sources, reinforcing the sustainability advantage of geothermal energy. The results highlight the potential for further environmental optimization, particularly through the integration of renewable electricity sources to power the compression system, thereby reducing indirect emissions.

For the cassava drying application, the performance analysis of Cycle A using R1234ze(Z) as the working fluid is presented in Fig. 9. This figure provides both the thermal load capacities of the hot springs under different operational scenarios and the corresponding economic and environmental implications. The graph on the left illustrates the thermal loads of each hot spring under three distinct scenarios, characterized by different flow rates: Low (Lm), Medium (Mm), and High (Hm). These scenarios are associated with increasing cassava drying capacities, denoted as CD_{10} , CD_{25} , and CD_{50} , respectively. The purple dotted line in the graph indicates these progressively higher drying capacities. Meanwhile, the right-side graph presents two key performance indicators: the LCOH on the left vertical axis and the CC indicator on the

right vertical axis.

A detailed analysis of the results reveals that not all hot springs can meet the CD_{10} drying capacity under Lm conditions. Specifically, only a subset of the evaluated hot springs—Madzimawira, Chombo, Chiwe, Motondolo 2, Mphizi Stream, and Chiweta—achieves the necessary thermal output to sustain this drying level. The remaining hot springs, under the same Lm conditions, are only able to sustain lower thermal loads, which directly impacts the amount of cassava that can be effectively dried using the available geothermal heat. However, when moving to the Mm scenario, the situation improves significantly. Under these conditions, all wells can reach the thermal level required for the CD_{10} drying capacity. Despite this improvement, not all hot springs are sufficient to achieve the CD_{25} drying level. Only a selected group of high-performing wells—Chombo, Chiwe, Motondolo, Motondolo 2, Mphizi Stream, and Chiweta—can meet this increased thermal demand, demonstrating their potential to sustain large-scale cassava drying operations.

At the highest drying capacity level, CD_{50} , only three wells—Chiwe, Motondolo 2, and Mphizi Stream—are capable of not only reaching but also exceeding the required thermal demand under Hm conditions. This distinction makes these three wells stand out as the most promising sources of geothermal heat for cassava drying applications. Their superior performance suggests that they could support even larger-scale drying processes beyond those considered in this study, offering reliable and sustainable energy for agro-industrial applications.

Beyond thermal performance, an economic and environmental evaluation is crucial to assess the feasibility of utilizing geothermal heat for cassava drying. Fig. 9 highlights several key observations related to both cost-effectiveness and environmental impact. The LCOH values for all hot springs fall within the range of $6.8\text{--}7.6\text{c}\$/\text{kWh}$, demonstrating a relatively low and competitive cost of thermal energy when compared to conventional systems. However, as indicated by the variation bars in the graph, specific wells—Ngala, Chikwizi, and July Borehole—can exhibit higher LCOH values exceeding $8\text{c}\$/\text{kWh}$ under low flow rate conditions. This increase in cost is primarily attributed to their lower geothermal resource temperatures, which directly affect productivity, leading to reduced energy output and increased cost per unit of heat produced.

The range of LCOH variation is generally between 1 % and 6 % across all scenarios. However, exceptions are observed in Chikwizi and July Borehole, where variations reach approximately 10 %. This increased fluctuation is again a consequence of their lower resource temperatures, which limit efficiency and elevate costs. Nonetheless, it is important to highlight that even in these cases, the LCOH remains consistently lower

Fig. 9. Heat produced by cycle A with R1234ze(Z) fluid and corresponding LCOH and CC, for Cassava drying.

than that of conventional heating systems, reinforcing the economic viability of geothermal energy for drying applications.

The same trend is reflected in the environmental impact analysis, where the CC indicator values are found to be highest for Ngala, Chikwizi, and July Borehole. A clear inverse relationship between CC values and resource temperature is observed, meaning that hot springs with higher geothermal temperatures exhibit lower environmental impact. This occurs because the functional unit used for comparison is energy output—lower temperature sources produce less thermal energy, requiring greater resource consumption to achieve the same heating effect, which in turn increases the carbon footprint per unit of energy.

Despite these variations, the overall CC values across all evaluated hot springs range between 131.4 g CO₂ eq/kWh and 138.8 g CO₂ eq/kWh. These values are consistently lower than those of conventional systems, reinforcing the environmental advantage of using geothermal heat in cassava drying applications. This finding is particularly relevant in the context of global efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and transition to more sustainable energy sources.

Fig. 10 provides a visual representation of the population density across Malawi, overlaid with the locations of the analyzed hot springs. This map serves as a crucial tool for assessing the potential reach of geothermal energy in the region, particularly in the context of its application for cooking stations. By integrating demographic data with the geographical distribution of thermal resources, the model effectively highlights the inhabited areas that could benefit from the heat generated by these wells. Each pixel on the map corresponds to a specific number of inhabitants, and by assuming an average daily thermal energy consumption of approximately 1.35 kWh per person, the model identifies those areas situated near the hot springs where the available thermal energy could be utilized. To visually distinguish between different resource capacities, the map employs varying shades of green, with darker shades representing areas with higher resource availability and lighter shades indicating lower capacities.

The analysis groups the hot springs into four distinct geographical areas, each with their own characteristics and potential for thermal

energy distribution. Area A includes the hot springs at Ngala, Mphizi Stream, and Chiweta. Among these, the Chiweta well alone possesses a thermal capacity sufficient to cover a substantial surface area of approximately 104 km². However, when the resources of Ngala and Mphizi Stream are considered, the total coverage expands significantly. Depending on the flow rate scenario, this combined resource can provide thermal energy over an area of 37.4 km² under low-flow conditions, 87.4 km² under medium-flow conditions, and up to 120.7 km² under high-flow conditions. This highlights the strong potential of these hot springs to supply energy to a sizable portion of the population.

Area B, which encompasses the Motondolo, Motondolo 2, and Chiwe wells, also exhibits a considerable ability to meet thermal demand. In this region, the extent of energy coverage is highly dependent on the available flow rate. Under the lowest flow conditions, the energy provided by these wells can sustain an area of 29.1 km². However, as the flow rate increases, so does the capacity to serve a broader area, reaching 124.8 km² in the medium-flow scenario and expanding to an impressive 212.3 km² under high-flow conditions. This demonstrates that these wells, when operating at higher capacities, have the potential to serve an even larger population base, further reinforcing their significance in the context of renewable thermal energy deployment.

Moving to Area C, which includes the hot springs at Chombo, Madzimawira, and Ling’ona, a slightly lower thermal capacity is observed in comparison to the previous areas. Here, the coverage varies considerably based on the flow rate. At low-flow conditions, these wells can serve an area of 156.65 km², while under medium-flow conditions, this coverage is reduced to 49.9 km², and under high-flow conditions, it reaches 83.2 km². Notably, within this group, the Chikwizi well demonstrates the lowest capacity for thermal energy distribution, with coverage limited to 8.3 km² in the low-flow scenario, 20.8 km² in the medium-flow scenario, and 37.46 km² in the high-flow scenario. These results suggest that, while this region does contribute to the overall geothermal energy potential, its role may be more limited compared to other high-performing hot springs.

Lastly, Area D consists of the July Borehole well, which has the most

Fig. 10. Thermal demand satisfaction map of hot-spring areas in Malawi. A: Ngala, Mphizi Stream and Chiweta B: Motondolo, Motondolo 2 and Chiwe C: Chombo, Madzimawira Ling’ona, Chikwizi D: July Borehole.

restricted coverage potential among the analyzed locations. Under high-flow conditions, this well can supply energy over a maximum area of 33.3 km². However, this coverage decreases as flow rates drop, with 20.8 km² of coverage under medium-flow conditions and a mere 4.16 km² under low-flow conditions. Given these limitations, this well alone would not be able to sustain large-scale applications but could still serve smaller, localized populations or be integrated into a broader network of geothermal resources.

From an overall perspective, the findings indicate that Areas A and B hold the greatest potential for geothermal energy distribution, largely due to the proximity of multiple high-capacity wells. These regions consistently demonstrate the ability to supply energy to significant portions of the population, with coverage areas remaining above 4 km², except in the case of the July Borehole under the low-flow scenario. In contrast, all other hot springs exhibit minimum coverage areas exceeding 8 km², reinforcing their viability for applications requiring a widespread and stable thermal energy supply.

The ability of these geothermal resources to provide energy for cooking stations is particularly relevant in the context of large-scale food preparation, where access to reliable and cost-effective heating is essential. However, the study also acknowledges certain limitations, particularly regarding the potential for using hot springs in agricultural applications. While geothermal heat is often employed for processes such as vegetable drying and other forms of food preservation, the lack of detailed data on Malawi's agricultural zones prevented a comprehensive assessment of this potential application. Despite this constraint, the results strongly suggest that the geothermal well system could play a vital role in meeting the energy needs of local populations, particularly for domestic and industrial food preparation purposes.

5. Conclusion

A comprehensive model capable of predicting the thermodynamic efficiencies, LCOH and environmental impacts associated with HTHPs coupled to geothermal energy sources has been realized and applied to an African case study. The analysis demonstrates the significant impact of drilling costs on LCOH, with deeper wells typically requiring higher investment. For instance, in scenarios with shallow wells, the LCOH can be as low as 11–13c\$/kWh, indicating strong cost-effectiveness. However, deeper drilling may lead to LCOH values exceeding 50c\$/kWh, needing careful consideration of well characteristics in economic assessments. Moreover, from an environmental point of view the analysis indicates that HTHP systems generally result in lower CC compared to conventional heating methods, particularly in scenarios with higher temperatures and optimized energy consumption.

The integration of economic (LCOH) and environmental (CC) metamodels offers a robust framework for evaluating HTHP systems. By normalizing against established reference values—17c\$/kWh for gas boilers and 223.88 g CO₂ eq/kWh for borehole heat exchangers—this approach defines a cost-benefit or impact-benefit ratio that clearly indicates when resource conditions deliver an economic or environmental advantage. Notably, the results highlight that economic feasibility—driven by factors such as initial capital expenditure, operational, and maintenance costs—plays a decisive role in system viability, often outweighing environmental considerations. Prioritizing the optimal conditions derived from the economic metamodels should be the primary benchmark for designing and implementing HTHP installations. This integrated framework not only enhances our understanding of the trade-offs between cost and environmental impact but also guides future project planning and investment decisions in geothermal energy systems.

The analyses conducted for the case study in Malawi reveal a significant potential in the utilization of high-temperature geothermal systems for various applications, including meeting the heat demand for cooking stations of different sizes and cassava drying. It has been demonstrated that even under the most unfavorable conditions,

geothermal systems can achieve high levels of thermal efficiency, with operating costs and environmental impacts significantly reduced compared to other conventional energy sources. Furthermore, the results indicate that the potential for greenhouse gas emissions reduction is largely influenced by the temperature of the geothermal fluid, which in turn reduces the electricity consumption associated with high-temperature heat pump cycles. Another way to further reduce this consumption is to exploit electricity from renewable sources, such as geothermal energy itself.

However, it is acknowledged that the decision to implement such systems should be guided not only by their economic efficiency but also by their overall environmental impact. Therefore, careful evaluation of both aspects is recommended to guide decisions regarding the selection and design of geothermal systems.

Moreover, the study highlights the significant potential of geothermal wells in Malawi to meet thermal energy demands, particularly in densely populated areas like areas close to the hot springs. With coverage consistently exceeding 8 km² in most scenarios, these resources prove their viability for applications such as food preparation, benefiting local communities. Further research could explore their use in agriculture, such as vegetable drying, to maximize their impact on sustainable energy solutions.

There are potential studies that could pave the way for future developments. This methodology could be redefined by incorporating more details into the modeling phase, examining factors such as the effect of the number of ribs on heat exchange or active techniques of heat transfer enhancement, thereby enabling even more precise optimization and design.

Alternatively, while maintaining the current level of modeling complexity, this approach has already been successfully applied to characterize a broader set of geothermal resources across the African continent within the framework of the European LEAP-RE project [46]. This demonstrates its scalability and adaptability, offering a robust foundation for broader applications. The methodology could be extended to additional geographic contexts by incorporating new geothermal scenarios or regions, thereby enabling comparative analyses across diverse locations. With adequate knowledge of geothermal resource characteristics, the model holds the potential to be scaled up and applied at the continental level, providing valuable insights into the feasibility and impact of geothermal deployment across Africa.

In situations where site-specific data is limited or unavailable, the model's flexibility allows for the use of input parameter uncertainty distributions. Through the integration of Monte Carlo simulations, it becomes possible to estimate a range of outcomes for both resource availability and associated metrics such as the ones analyzed in this study, LCOH and CC. This probabilistic approach enhances the model's applicability under data-scarce conditions and increases the robustness of its output.

Future work could enrich the environmental dimension of the analysis by incorporating additional impact categories beyond Climate Change, such as water use, human toxicity, and ecosystem effects. This would allow for a more holistic sustainability assessment and help identify potential trade-offs or synergies among environmental objectives.

Moreover, further developments of the methodology could involve the integration of the model with Geographic Information System (GIS) platforms. This would enable the spatial visualization of geothermal potential, the creation of resource exploitation maps, and the formulation of geospatial indicators for resource potential, technical and economic viability, and development priorities. Such integration would be especially valuable for aligning geothermal resource planning with the rapidly growing energy demand and regional development goals throughout the African continent.

In conclusion, the comprehensive evaluation of thermodynamic, economic and environmental factors highlights the potential of high temperature heat pump systems as a sustainable solution for various

heating applications. The results suggest a multidisciplinary approach that balances economic considerations with environmental sustainability to maximize the benefits of HTHP technology in real-world implementations. Finally, the effectiveness of the developed metamodelling of energy systems, such as the HTHP here analyzed, must be remarked for their profitable use in georeferenced applications at large scale level where the thermodynamic, economic and environmental assessment of different proposed solutions for the local available resources is carried out. Such tools are extremely interesting for investors, stakeholders and decision makers needing a large scale assessment of technologies for the sustainable exploitation of geothermal resources at the service of local activities and population.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used Chat GPT in order to improve readability and revise possible grammatical errors. After using this tool, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Zuffi Claudio: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Fiaschi Daniele:** Funding acquisition, Investigation, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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